

ISic0617

I.Sicily inscription 0617

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Morgantina

Place of origin (modern)

Morgantina

Provenance

From the North Stoa of the Agora

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Aidone, Museo Archeologico di
Aidone

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 644873

Bibliography

Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 356 n.97

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